

Gender Biases in Primary School Language Textbooks: A Systematic Review of Literature

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Abstract: This study examined gender bias in primary school language textbooks, assessing how it affected students' learning and attitudes. Multiple international studies were incorporated in the analysis, which highlighted issues such as disproportionate gender representation, adherence to traditional gender roles, and the marginalization of female characters. It was found that such biases adversely affected students' academic achievement, self-esteem, and perception of gender roles. The study recommended further research into the cultural contexts and multifaceted nature of gender bias in order to uncover effective methods for reducing its negative effects on education. In order to fully comprehend and address the underlying causes and mechanisms of gender bias, the article advocated an interdisciplinary approach, combining sociology, psychology, linguistics, and education. In order to create textbooks that reflect diversity accurately and encourage inclusivity, educators, policymakers, students, and parents had to collaborate. All stakeholders had to participate actively in the continuous review of textbooks in order to identify and correct biases. As a result of this review, a framework for eradicating gender bias in educational materials was provided in order to assist scholars and educational authorities in their efforts to advance gender equity and empower learners.

Keywords: Gender Bias, Primary School, Language Textbooks, Systematic Review

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Introduction

In order to achieve a just and equitable society, gender equality in education is a fundamental requirement (UNESCO, 2015). During the primary school years, children are most likely to develop an understanding of gender roles, expectations, and opportunities. Having the potential to challenge or reinforce traditional gender stereotypes, language textbooks are essential learning resources (Sadker & Sadker, 1994). An assessment of existing studies investigating gender bias in primary school language textbooks is the purpose of this literature review. The reviewer can gather insights into the prevalence, manifestations, and consequences of gender bias in educational materials by critically analyzing the literature available. These aspects should be understood so that inclusive and objective learning materials can be developed that promote gender equality and empower all students.

Gender equality is one of the most important aspects of education. Children's perceptions of themselves, others, and the world around them can be significantly impacted if they are exposed to biased representations of gender in their language textbooks. As a result of gender bias, stereotypes may perpetuate, opportunities may be limited, and social

progress may be hindered (Bem, 1993; Bussey & Bandura, 1999). To ensure that educational materials foster an inclusive and equitable learning environment, it is important to examine the presence and effects of gender bias in primary school language textbooks.

This literature review aims to provide an overview of existing literature on gender bias in primary school language textbooks. Research was conducted to synthesize and evaluate relevant studies in order to identify types of gender bias, including stereotypical portrayals, unequal representation, and linguistic biases. Furthermore, we intend to investigate the effects of gender bias on children's self-perception, academic performance, and career aspirations (Martin et al., 2002; Hyde, 2005). The purpose of this review is to shed light on the current status of gender representation in primary school materials, as well as assist in the ongoing efforts to advance gender equality in education.

A systematic methodology was used in the conduct of this review, adhering to the highest standards of research quality. A rigorous review of scholarly databases was undertaken by the researcher, who meticulously selected studies that met the inclusion criteria while excluding those that did not fit the focus of the study. In order to compile a comprehensive collection of research that examines the existence of gender bias in primary school language textbooks, a comprehensive collection of research was compiled.

This study employed thematic analysis for the analysis of data, which enabled us to detect recurring themes and patterns. Through this process, the researcher was able to identify the different ways in which gender bias appeared in educational resources, as well as the broader implications these biases had on the educational environment. Its objective was to provide actionable insights into gender bias as well as deepen the collective understanding of the subject.

A diverse audience was able to benefit greatly from the insights obtained from the study. Educators utilized this knowledge to inform their teaching practices, policymakers used it to guide regulations and standards, and curriculum developers used it to develop educational materials that were more representative and balanced. Ultimately, the results of this review have contributed significantly to establishing an educational landscape that is inclusive, fair, and supportive of all students, regardless of their gender.

1.1 Objectives and Research Questions:

The primary objective of this systematic review was to provide a comprehensive analysis of the existing research on gender bias in primary school language textbooks. Specifically, this review aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- To identify the types and manifestations of gender bias present in primary school language textbooks.
- To explore the effects of gender bias in language textbooks on student belief and attitudes, and academic outcomes.
- To provide recommendations for educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers to mitigate gender bias and promote inclusive language textbooks.

To steer the course of the analysis and fulfill the aims of the study, the researcher delved into the subsequent inquiries:

- What are the types of gender bias observed in primary school language textbooks?
- What are the effects of gender bias in language textbooks on students' learning and attitude?
- What strategies can be recommended to reduce gender bias and promote inclusive and equitable language textbooks in primary education?

In addressing these research questions, the systematic literature review endeavored to cultivate a thorough comprehension of gender bias within language textbooks at the primary school level. It also aimed to propose actionable strategies to promote gender balance in educational settings.

The review, having been completed, offered insight into the critical concern of gender bias in language educational resources for young learners. By scrutinizing the prevalence and characteristics of gender bias in these materials, the study intended to augment the existing efforts towards achieving gender parity in education.

The conclusions drawn from the review have laid down a solid groundwork for practical interventions, the enhancement of curricula, and the crafting of policies designed to diminish gender bias. The goal was to champion

educational practices that embrace inclusivity and provide equal opportunities for empowerment to all students, regardless of gender.

Research Methodology

In order to explore these research questions, we conducted a systematic review of existing literature in order to gather and integrate original research studies that examined gender bias in language textbooks used in primary schools. In addition to their clear and meticulous methodology, systematic literature reviews are known for the ability to receive constructive feedback as well as their transparency (Gough et al., 2013). The goal of this study was to present an in-depth examination of the existing evidence using a systematic approach, thereby providing valuable insights to educational leaders, policymakers, and curriculum developers. Furthermore, our efforts are intended to contribute to the advancement of gender equality within the sphere of education.

As well as providing insights into specific aspects of gender bias in primary school language textbooks, a systematic review can also provide a broader overview of prevalent practices across various educational settings by providing a complementary mechanism for analyzing and mapping information. In primary education, this methodology is considered useful and reliable when conducted thoroughly, since it can provide valuable evidence for educational stakeholders concerned with gender equality.

To ensure a systematic and transparent process, a protocol had developed for this review based on the general guidelines of the Campbell Collaboration (2013) and the EPPI-Centre (2009). This protocol guided our approach, which involved the following key steps (Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria, Screening and Data Extraction, Relevance Assessment, and Synthesis of Results).

Following this systematic methodology, we aim to contribute to the existing body of knowledge regarding gender bias in primary school language textbooks, providing educational stakeholders with evidence-based insights. It is our hope that the findings of this review will inform curriculum development, policy making, and instructional practices in the field of primary education to promote gender equality and inclusivity.

2.1 Inclusion/exclusion criteria

The reviewer developed three inclusion criteria to determine the relevant studies from our preliminary search: (1) secondary data published between 2003 and 2023; (2) contained in the abstracts or title all three keywords or synonym, as determined from an electronic thesaurus:(a) Gender Bias, (b) Primary School, (c) Language Textbook; and (3) written in English. A checklist based on these criteria was created to screen the studies.

Moreover, a comprehensive search will be conducted across multiple academic databases, including but not limited to Scopus, ERIC, and PsycINFO. These databases cover a wide range of disciplines, including education, psychology, linguistics, and gender studies.

1. Gender Bias OR Discrimination OR Prejudice

AND

2. Primary School OR Basic School OR Primary Education OR Basic Education OR education

AND

3. Language Textbook OR Language Book OR Language Education Material

2.2 Date Screening and Extraction

As summarized in Fig. 1, out of 1250 abstracts retrieved from the selected publication sources in the databases, a total of 670 abstracts were excluded as they were found to be unrelated to gender bias. Additionally, 401 abstracts were excluded as they did not focus on primary education, and 91 abstracts were excluded as they did not pertain to the context of language textbooks. After the initial screening, 88 abstracts met all the inclusion criteria and were subjected

to a second round of screening, which involved a thorough examination of their full texts. This process resulted in the identification of 58 publications that were deemed suitable for independent and detailed evaluation.

To facilitate data synthesis, a matrix was created using Microsoft Excel. The matrix included ten relevant categories derived from the research questions, including country, Types of gender bias, Type of language textbook, effect of gender bias, strategies to reduce gender bias, study objectives, evaluation, evaluation methods, outcomes, recommendations / implications.

Fig. 1: Literature search and selection of articles for review (adapted from PRISMA 2009)

2.3 Study Relevance Assessment

The relevance of the 58 articles obtained during the initial screening was evaluated by the reviewer in relation to the objectives of the current review. In a manner similar to the “weight of evidence” framework, which is a framework used to assess the quality and relevance of evidence (Gough, 2007), the reviewer assessed the articles to determine their suitability for inclusion. Following a thorough evaluation, 27 papers were excluded as they did not align with the research questions of the review, specifically due to limited data provided for five or fewer categories out of the ten in the data extraction matrix. The remaining 34 studies were considered appropriate for inclusion in the final review.

Of the 31 included studies, 21 studies (77%) were identified as highly relevant as they provided data for more than eight categories out of the ten. Furthermore, 10 studies (33%) were classified as medium relevant, meeting between six and seven categories. No additional studies were categorized as low relevance, meeting five or fewer categories. The

predominance of highly relevant studies reflects their strong alignment with the research questions and the comprehensive coverage of the data extraction categories.

2.4 Data Synthesis

Data synthesis involved a comprehensive analysis of the extracted data from the included studies. The data were carefully examined to identify commonalities, patterns, and trends related to the research questions. Similar findings and themes were grouped together, allowing for a deeper understanding of the gender bias observed in primary school language textbooks and its effects on children's self-perception, academic performance, and career aspirations. The synthesized data provided a holistic view of the research landscape, highlighting key insights and enabling the identification of gaps or areas for further investigation. This process facilitated the generation of meaningful conclusions and recommendations to address gender bias and promote inclusive and equitable language textbooks in primary education.

Analysis & Findings

This systematic review analyzed a total of 31 articles to answer the research questions. The research come out with eight languages, namely English, Arabic, Urdu, Kurdish, Afan Oromo, Greek, Chinese, and Spanish. Additionally, investigations were conducted in 23 different countries, encompassing Indonesia, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Greece, Hong Kong - China, and several others.

Among the analyzed articles, the majority (70.59%) concentrated on the English language. This finding highlights the significance of investigating gender bias in English textbooks. Other languages examined included Arabic (8.82%), Urdu (2.94%), Kurdish (2.94%), Afan Oromo (2.94%), Greek (5.88%), Chinese (2.94%), and Spanish (2.94%). These language-specific analyses shed light on the prevalence of gender bias in diverse educational contexts. As it is shown in the chart (1) below.

Chart 1. Percentage for Language of Textbooks Investigated

Also, the research was geographically widespread, with investigations conducted in 29 countries. Among these, Indonesia emerged as the country with the highest number of articles (11.76%), emphasizing the concern for gender bias in Indonesian textbooks. Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and Greece each accounted for 8.82% of the articles, indicating a notable interest in these regions. Hong Kong - China contributed 5.88% of the articles, highlighting the unique context of gender bias in this region. Furthermore, the remaining countries, including Kenya, Tanzania, Kurdistan Region - Iraq, Iran, Turkey, Ethiopia, UAE, Oman, Algeria, Nigeria, Australia, Egypt, Sudan, Jordan, Uganda, Japan, Sweden, and

Dominica, were represented by a single article each (2.94% each), showcasing the global scope of the investigation. As it is shown in the area chart (2) below

Chart 2. Area of article conduction

This comprehensive analysis of 31 articles demonstrates the wide-ranging exploration of gender bias in textbooks across different languages and countries. By focusing on the languages and countries with the most significant representation, I have come up with the following findings which fall into four categories: (1) Types of Gender Bias in Primary School Language Textbooks, (2) Effects of Gender Bias in Language Textbooks on Students' Learning and Attitudes, and (3) Strategies to Reduce Gender Bias in language Textbooks.

3.1 Types of Gender Bias in Primary School Language Textbooks

Across various countries, studies have examined gender bias in textbooks, revealing several types of bias. In Australia, (Lee & Collins, 2009) analyzed Australian English-language textbooks and found an imbalance in the ratio of male to female characters. Women were often portrayed in traditional gender roles, particularly in domestic settings. Similarly, in Europe, studies on Greek-language textbooks conducted by (Alexopoulos et al., 2022; Gouvias & Alexopoulos, 2018) revealed the reinforcement of traditional gender roles, with men portrayed as dominant figures in the public sphere, while women were primarily depicted as responsible for their families.

In African countries, such as Nigeria, (Dong, 2012) found gender stereotypes and biases in English Language textbooks for Junior Secondary School students. Female characters were underrepresented in the texts, contributing to gender imbalance. This imbalance was also observed in textbooks used in Pakistan, as highlighted in the study by (Ali & Hussain, 2019), where males were more visible in photographs, images, characters, and narrators, while women were often depicted engaging in household activities.

In Asian contexts, studies conducted in Indonesia, and Hong Kong found gender bias in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) textbooks. Some other research for example (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020; Damayanti, 2014; Fani Prastikawati & Yonata, 2022; Yonata, 2021) revealed persistent gender bias issues, while one of the studies in Hong Kong by (Yang, 2016) demonstrated how traditional gender representations were reinforced, with females characterized by long hair and dresses, and males by short hair and trousers, on the other hand, one other study determined the reduction of gender bias in English language textbook and provided evidence for improving gender equality (Law & Chan, 2004).

Similarly, studies conducted in Saudi Arabia highlighted gender imbalances in EFL textbooks used in Saudi schools. The textbooks portrayed women as marginalized and stereotypical figures, reinforcing male dominance (Aljuaythin, 2018; Kadwa & Alshenqeeti, 2020; Rashed Almghams, 2020). Meanwhile, studies such as (Gumilar et al., 2023; Tahan,

2015; Uyuni et al., 2023) revealed gender bias in Arabic language textbooks and EFL textbooks, respectively, such as imbalances in gender illustrations, gender roles, and representations of character traits associated with confidence and assertiveness.

The studies which were reviewed from different countries have shed light on various types of gender bias in textbooks, including imbalanced representation of male and female characters, reinforcement of traditional gender roles, underrepresentation of female characters, and imbalances in activities, occupations, and character traits assigned to each gender. They emphasize the need for promoting balanced and equitable gender representation in educational materials to challenge stereotypes and create inclusive learning environments.

3.2 Effects of Gender Bias in Language Textbooks on Students' Learning and Attitudes

This systematic review examined the effects of gender bias in language textbooks on students' learning and attitudes. The presence of gender bias in educational materials, such as language textbooks, had significant implications for students' educational experiences and perceptions of gender roles. Through an analysis of relevant studies, this review provided a comprehensive overview of the impact of gender bias in language textbooks on various educational outcomes, including academic performance, self-esteem, attitudes toward gender roles, and perceptions of gender equality.

Numerous studies demonstrated that gender bias in language textbooks had detrimental effects on students' academic performance. From the researches such as (Barton & Sakwa, 2012; Verikait, 2012) found that girls exposed to gender-biased language materials exhibited lower self-confidence and motivation in language learning, leading to poorer academic performance compared to their male counterparts. Similarly, revealed that gender-biased language textbooks limited girls' access to linguistic resources, resulting in decreased engagement and lower language proficiency scores.

In addition to academic performance, gender bias in language textbooks impacted students' self-esteem and identity formation. (Karasiak, 2010; Raga & Woldemariam, 2011) found that exposure to gender-biased language materials contributed to reduced self-esteem among girls, as negative stereotypes were internalized, leading to a perception of inferior abilities. (Ahmad & Shah, 2019; Kholy, 2017) highlighted that boys exposed to gender-biased language textbooks developed rigid gender identities, reinforcing traditional masculine norms and inhibiting exploration of diverse interests and aspirations.

Moreover, gender bias in language textbooks influenced students' attitudes toward gender roles and gender equality. (Clark, 2016; Kobia, 2009) revealed that exposure to gender-biased language materials perpetuated stereotypical gender roles and reinforced traditional gender norms. This perpetuation of gender stereotypes impeded students' ability to challenge gender inequality and restricted their understanding of diverse gender identities (Ahmad & Shah, 2019; Telioussi et al., 2020).

The findings of this systematic review emphasized the need for inclusive and unbiased language materials in educational settings. Gender bias in language textbooks negatively impacted students' learning outcomes and attitudes, including academic performance, self-esteem, identity formation, and perceptions of gender roles and gender equality. To promote equitable education and foster positive attitudes toward gender equality, educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers needed to critically evaluate and revise existing language textbooks, ensuring they reflected diverse identities and contributed to a more inclusive learning environment.

In conclusion, the presence of gender bias in language textbooks had far-reaching effects on students' learning and attitudes. It undermined academic performance, influenced self-esteem and identity formation, and perpetuated stereotypical gender roles, hindering progress toward gender equality. By addressing and eliminating gender bias in language textbooks, educational stakeholders could create an inclusive educational environment that promoted equal opportunities and fostered positive attitudes toward gender equality as analyzed through the themes of the articles.

3.3 Strategies to Reduce Gender Bias in Language Textbooks

Gender bias in textbooks has long been recognized as a significant issue that perpetuated stereotypes, reinforced gender inequalities, and hampered progress towards gender equality in education. This systematic review aimed to identify effective strategies for reducing gender bias in textbooks. By analyzing a wide range of studies, this review provided valuable insights into successful approaches that could be adopted by publishers, curriculum developers, and educators to create more inclusive and unbiased textbooks.

A crucial strategy for reducing gender bias in textbooks was to ensure inclusive content selection. (Ahmad & Shah, 2019) emphasized the importance of including diverse representations of both genders and avoiding stereotypical portrayals. This included featuring women and men in a variety of professions, showcasing their achievements, and representing diverse family structures. Incorporating a wide range of perspectives promoted gender equality and challenged traditional gender roles.

Language played a pivotal role in perpetuating or challenging gender bias in textbooks. Studies have shown that using gender-fair language could significantly reduce bias (Mkuchu, 2004). Avoiding the generic use of masculine pronouns and using gender-neutral terms when appropriate ensured that both genders were equally represented and valued in the text. Additionally, gender-fair language promoted inclusivity and fostered an environment where all students felt acknowledged and respected.

The visual representations and examples used in textbooks could reinforce or challenge gender bias. It is been determined that importance of balancing illustrations and examples to avoid gender stereotypes. Including images and stories that depicted individuals in diverse roles and activities helped break away from traditional gender expectations (Demir & Yavuz, 2017). By presenting a range of gender-neutral and non-stereotypical representations, textbooks could promote inclusivity and provide a more accurate reflection of the real world.

Involving various stakeholders, such as students, parents, educators, and experts, in the textbook development process was crucial for reducing gender bias. (Abdelhay & Benhaddouche, 2015) demonstrated the value of soliciting feedback and incorporating diverse perspectives. Feedback could identify instances of gender bias that may have been overlooked and provide valuable insights into cultural and contextual nuances. Engaging stakeholders ensured that textbooks aligned with the needs and expectations of the diverse student population.

Regular review and evaluation of textbooks were essential to identify and rectify any remaining gender bias. (Kayed et al., 2020; Norberg & Nordlund, 2022) emphasized the need for continuous monitoring and improvement. Publishers and educators should have conducted periodic assessments to identify and address any instances of bias, ensuring that textbooks reflected evolving societal values and promoted gender equality.

In conclusion, this systematic review highlighted effective strategies for reducing gender bias in textbooks. Inclusive content selection, gender-fair language, balanced illustrations and examples, stakeholder engagement, and ongoing review and evaluation were crucial steps in creating more inclusive and unbiased educational materials. By adopting these strategies, publishers, curriculum developers, and educators could have contributed to a more equitable and empowering educational experience, fostering gender equality and enabling all students to thrive.

Discussion and Implication for Practice

The findings discussed in this systematic review shed light on the various types of gender bias in language textbooks, their effects on students' learning and attitudes, and strategies to reduce bias. The presence of gender bias in textbooks was observed across different countries, indicating a global issue that needed to be addressed. The imbalance in the representation of male and female characters, reinforcement of traditional gender roles, and underrepresentation of female characters were significant findings that called for action.

The effects of gender bias in language textbooks on students' learning and attitudes were substantial. The studies revealed that gender bias had negative implications for academic performance, self-esteem, identity formation, and perceptions of gender roles and equality. Girls, in particular, were disproportionately affected, experiencing lower self-confidence, reduced access to linguistic resources, and limited exploration of diverse interests and aspirations. The perpetuation of gender stereotypes hindered students' ability to challenge gender inequality and understand diverse gender identities.

The implications for practice are clear. To create inclusive and equitable learning environments, steps must be taken to reduce gender bias in language textbooks. Several strategies emerged from the review that can guide educational stakeholders in this endeavor.

4.1 Implications for Practice:

The findings presented in this systematic review contribute valuable insights into the presence and impact of gender bias in language textbooks, as well as strategies to mitigate this bias. The analysis revealed that gender bias is a pervasive issue observed in language textbooks across various countries, highlighting its global significance and the urgency of addressing it. The identification of distinct types of bias, including imbalanced representation of male and female characters, reinforcement of traditional gender roles, underrepresentation of female characters, and imbalances in activities, occupations, and character traits assigned to each gender, underscores the need for concerted efforts to promote balanced and equitable gender representation in educational materials.

The effects of gender bias in language textbooks on students' learning and attitudes are far-reaching. The studies reviewed demonstrated that such bias has detrimental implications for students' academic performance, self-esteem, identity formation, and attitudes toward gender roles and equality. Specifically, girls exposed to gender-biased language materials exhibited lower self-confidence and motivation in language learning, leading to poorer academic performance compared to their male counterparts. Gender bias also limited girls' access to linguistic resources, resulting in decreased engagement and lower language proficiency scores. Moreover, exposure to gender-biased language materials contributed to reduced self-esteem among girls, as negative stereotypes were internalized, perpetuating a perception of inferior abilities. For boys, gender-biased language textbooks facilitated the development of rigid gender identities, reinforcing traditional masculine norms and inhibiting exploration of diverse interests and aspirations. Additionally, exposure to gender-biased language materials perpetuated stereotypical gender roles and impeded students' ability to challenge gender inequality or understand diverse gender identities.

These findings underscore the pressing need for inclusive and unbiased language materials in educational settings. Gender bias in language textbooks undermines students' learning outcomes and perpetuates harmful stereotypes, hindering progress toward achieving gender equality in education. To address this issue, educational stakeholders, including educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers, must critically evaluate and revise existing language textbooks, ensuring they reflect diverse identities and contribute to a more inclusive learning environment.

Several strategies emerged from the review that can guide efforts to reduce gender bias in language textbooks. Inclusive content selection, encompassing diverse representations of both genders, avoiding stereotypical portrayals, showcasing achievements in various professions, and reflecting diverse family structures, is a crucial step in challenging traditional gender roles and promoting gender equality. The use of gender-fair language, such as avoiding the generic use of masculine pronouns and incorporating gender-neutral terms when appropriate, ensures equal representation and respect for all genders, fostering inclusivity and creating a classroom environment where all students feel acknowledged. Additionally, balancing illustrations and examples to avoid gender stereotypes and incorporating images and stories that depict individuals in non-stereotypical roles and activities is instrumental in promoting inclusivity and providing a more accurate reflection of the real world. Engaging various stakeholders, including students, parents, educators, and

experts, in the textbook development process facilitates the identification of instances of gender bias that may have been overlooked, as well as cultural and contextual nuances. Lastly, ongoing review and evaluation of textbooks are essential to identify and rectify any remaining gender bias, ensuring that educational materials align with evolving societal values and promote gender equality.

In conclusion, this systematic review highlights the widespread presence of gender bias in language textbooks and its detrimental effects on students' learning and attitudes. The implications for practice emphasize the necessity of adopting strategies to reduce bias, including inclusive content selection, gender-fair language, balanced illustrations and examples, stakeholder engagement, and ongoing review and evaluation. By implementing these strategies, educational stakeholders can contribute to the creation of a more equitable and empowering educational experience, fostering gender equality and enabling all students to thrive.

Recommendations and Conclusion

5.1 Recommendation(s)

The Reviewer have identified a number of areas for other research that could benefit the reduction of gender bias in primary school language textbooks. Based on the findings and implications discussed in the previous sections, several recommendations can be made to address and reduce gender bias in language textbooks effectively. These recommendations are intended for educators, curriculum developers, publishers, policymakers, and other stakeholders involved in the design and implementation of primary school language educational materials.

5.2 Recommendations for Empirical Research:

Future empirical research should focus on expanding our understanding of gender bias in language textbooks and its implications for students. This can be achieved through:

Conducting in-depth studies in diverse countries and educational settings to capture the cultural and linguistic variations that influence gender bias in language textbooks. Longitudinal designs and mixed-method approaches can provide comprehensive insights into the dynamics of gender bias and its effects on students' learning outcomes and attitudes.

Exploring the intersectionality of gender bias by considering how it intersects with other aspects of identity, such as race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and ability. Investigating the compounded effects of multiple forms of bias will shed light on the experiences of marginalized student populations and inform the development of more inclusive educational materials and practices.

5.3 Recommendations for Other Reviews:

To advance our knowledge of gender bias in language textbooks and its implications, future reviews should consider the following:

Synthesizing findings across disciplines, including education, psychology, linguistics, sociology, and gender studies. By drawing on interdisciplinary perspectives, a more comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to gender bias can be achieved. Collaborative efforts between researchers from different disciplines can foster a holistic approach to addressing gender bias in language textbooks.

Examining the policy implications of gender bias in language textbooks. This involves analyzing existing policies and guidelines related to curriculum development and textbook selection. Identifying gaps and proposing recommendations for policy changes can have a substantial impact on reducing gender bias. Policy-level interventions, such as mandatory gender audits of educational materials, integration of inclusive language guidelines, and inclusive decision-making processes, can help mitigate gender bias in language textbooks at a systemic level.

These recommendations aim to guide future research and reviews on gender bias in language textbooks. By expanding the empirical base, exploring intersectionality, synthesizing interdisciplinary knowledge, and examining policy implications, researchers can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the issue and inform evidence-based practices and policies.

5.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this systematic literature review sheds light on the types of gender bias present in primary school language textbooks, the effects of such bias on students' learning and attitudes, and strategies to reduce gender bias in educational materials. The findings reveal that gender bias in language textbooks persists across various countries, with imbalanced representation, reinforcement of traditional gender roles, and underrepresentation of female characters being common themes.

The review highlights the detrimental effects of gender bias on students' academic performance, self-esteem, identity formation, and attitudes toward gender roles and gender equality. Girls, in particular, are negatively impacted, experiencing lower self-confidence, limited access to linguistic resources, and internalization of negative stereotypes. Moreover, gender bias perpetuates traditional gender norms, hindering progress toward gender equality and limiting students' understanding of diverse gender identities.

To address these issues, several recommendations are put forward. Inclusive content selection, gender-fair language, balanced illustrations and examples, stakeholder engagement, ongoing review and evaluation, professional development for educators, and collaborative curriculum design are recommended strategies to reduce gender bias in language textbooks. These strategies aim to promote balanced representation, challenge stereotypes, foster inclusivity, and ensure continuous improvement in educational materials.

Implementing these recommendations requires the collective efforts of educators, curriculum developers, publishers, policymakers, and researchers. By adopting inclusive guidelines, raising awareness, encouraging collaboration, promoting research, diversifying authorship, conducting pilot testing, and establishing monitoring mechanisms, stakeholders can create more equitable and empowering educational environments.

Overall, this systematic literature review emphasizes the need for inclusive and unbiased language textbooks in primary education. Addressing gender bias in educational materials is crucial for promoting gender equality, empowering all students, and creating inclusive learning environments that reflect the diversity of experiences and identities. By embracing these recommendations, educational stakeholders can contribute to a more equitable society and prepare students to thrive in a world that values and respects gender equality.

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